

The Effect of Firm Size and Financial Leverage on the Corporate Cash Holding Behaviour of Listed Firms in Vietnam's Transport Sector

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Abstract

Background: Research on cash holding behaviour in emerging markets is limited, particularly in capital-intensive sectors such as transportation.

Objective: This paper examines the impact of firm size and financial leverage on cash-holding behaviour among listed transport firms in Vietnam, aiming to provide insights for enhancing corporate financial management in capital-intensive sectors.

Methodology: Research data were gathered from 60 transport firms listed on the Vietnam Stock Exchange between 2016 and 2023. The study utilises OLS, FEM, and REM models to analyse the impact of two primary independent variables (firm size - SIZAS and financial leverage - LEVE) on corporate cash-holding behaviours, as well as GLS regression to address the model's shortcomings. We incorporate control variables that correspond to both internal and external factors of the firm, including return on total assets (ROA), market-to-book ratio (MTBR), debt maturity (DEBM), current ratio (CURR), firm age (FAGE), market-to-book (MTB), real interest rate (RIR), inflation (INF), and GDP growth (GDP). Two indicators represent corporate cash-holding behaviour: the cash holding ratio (CASHD) and the cash ratio (CASHCL); therefore, two regression models are analysed.

Result: The main results of the study indicate that firm size has a negative influence on the cash ratio, but it does not significantly affect the cash holding ratio. In contrast, financial leverage shows a negative relationship with the cash holding ratio but has no significant impact on the cash ratio.

Conclusion: In the emerging markets' transportation sector, larger firms enjoy improved access to finance, diminishing the necessity to retain cash. Firms with elevated debt ratios often face significant financial costs, thereby depleting their cash reserves.

Unique Contribution: The study adds sector-specific evidence to the literature on cash management in emerging markets.

Key Recommendation: Future studies could broaden their focus to include additional macroeconomic variables and sectors, offering a more comprehensive perspective.

Keywords: Corporate cash holding behaviour, firm size, financial leverage, transport sector, Vietnam

Introduction

The current context of the global political economy has generated significant dynamics for research into Corporate Cash Holding (CCH) behaviour. Cash is a critical component within the assets section of every firm's balance sheet, being the most liquid yet least profitable asset. (Ali et al., 2016). The term "cash-rich firm" refers to companies that maintain substantial cash

reserves on their balance sheets. Liquidity Preference Theory has demonstrated that the reasons for holding cash stem from three essential motives: transaction, precautionary, and speculative motives. Cash-rich firms ensure they maintain adequate liquidity to cover short-term expenses, minimise transaction costs associated with converting other assets into cash, and seize opportunities (Ahrends et al., 2018; Amess et al., 2015). However, holding money in banks results in a loss of value over time due to the time value of money. Some managers are concerned that "money can burn a hole in their pocket". With abundant cash reserves, management might pursue ill-advised or lower-quality acquisitions. (Ali et al., 2016). Therefore, they advocate for the imposition of self-discipline in the decision-making process. The dual nature of cash drives research into the determinants of CCH behaviour across different economies and even among various industries.

This study aims to address the following questions: (1) Do firm size and financial leverage influence the cash-holding behaviour of listed transportation companies in Vietnam? and (2) If so, what is the degree and trend of their impact? Various firm-specific and macroeconomic factors have affected CCH's behaviour. Among these, the size of the firm and its leverage play crucial roles, as they influence cash-holding decisions according to financial theories. According to trade-off theory, companies balance the opportunity costs of retaining too much cash against the advantages of having cash on hand. Due to more varied businesses and easier access to outside funding, larger companies are probably going to keep less cash on hand than smaller ones. The pecking order theory further explains that companies prefer using internal funding over external funding. This results in more leveraged companies having less cash, as they rely on debt financing rather than retained earnings. Conversely, financial constraint theory argues that firms with high leverage and limited financing options tend to hold more cash as a precautionary measure. Given these opposing theoretical implications, knowing how business size and leverage affect CCH is crucial, especially in emerging economies with more pronounced financial constraints.

The primary motivation for conducting this study arises from the crucial role of financial reserves in supporting transport firms operating within a volatile business environment. The transport sector is significantly influenced by macroeconomic fluctuations, fuel price volatility, and market demand. These firms operate in an environment characterised by considerable asymmetric information, face substantial cash flow and business risks, and typically work with high financial and operational leverage. Maintaining an appropriate level of cash holdings enables firms to ensure liquidity, mitigate financial risks, and sustain stable operations. However, excessive cash holdings may result in high opportunity costs due to inefficient capital utilisation, whereas insufficient cash reserves may impede firms' ability to cope with financial shocks.

The second motivation for this study is the research gap that exists in the context of an emerging economy, such as Vietnam, regarding corporate cash holding behaviour. The majority of current research on cash-holding behaviour concentrates on developed economies (Aftab et al., 2018), where financial markets are more developed and firms have more convenient access to external capital. There are very few studies on this issue in emerging markets, such as Thakur and Kannadhasan (2019) and Diaw (2021). However, Vietnam, as an emerging economy, possesses an incomplete financial system, which leads firms to encounter numerous limitations in raising capital alongside a more challenging business environment. This raises the question of whether publicly listed transport companies in Vietnam exhibit different cash-holding behaviours compared to their counterparts in developed economies.

Literature Review

Firm size and CCH behaviour

Previous academic studies indicate a strong correlation between firm size and CCH. However, the link between firm size and CCH remains uncertain. Empirical research indicates both a negative correlation (Tayem, 2017) and a positive correlation (Diaw, 2021). If firm size serves as an indicator of information asymmetry, which in turn influences the costs associated with external financing, one should anticipate a negative correlation with capital holdings. Nevertheless, if firm size is regarded as an indicator of financial distress, it follows that smaller firms are more susceptible to liquidation in the event of experiencing financial difficulties. Consequently, such firms maintain higher cash reserves to mitigate the risk of encountering distressing situations. Given their access to knowledge asymmetries and economies of scale, we predict that smaller (larger) firms in an emerging market such as Vietnam maintain higher (lower) cash balances to manage every transaction and operation. This leads to our first hypothesis.

H1: A negative association exists between firm size and CCH behaviour.

Leverage and CCH behaviour

The predicted relationship between CCH and leverage is ambiguous. Bagh et al. (2021) found a positive relationship between corporate cash holdings (CCH) and leverage (LEVE) in China; however, this relationship is negative in Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India. Tayem (2017) provided empirical evidence of a non-linear relationship between leverage and cash holdings. Specifically, at lower levels of leverage, an increase in debt is associated with a reduction in cash reserves. However, as leverage rises beyond a certain threshold, this relationship reverses, and firms tend to hold more cash. This shift can be attributed to the heightened risk of financial distress faced by highly leveraged firms, which motivates them to accumulate cash as a precautionary measure to mitigate potential distress-related costs. Building upon existing literature, we hypothesise an inverse association between leverage and CCH. Our second hypothesis is:

H2: Leverage is negatively correlated with CCH behaviour.

Firm Characteristics and CCH Behaviour

Six firm characteristics, determinants of CCH behaviour, found in the literature, are used for the analysis. Besides the two factors, firm size and leverage, the other CCH determinants used in the study are: Return on total assets (ROA), Market-to-Book Ratio (MTBR), Debt Maturity (DEBM), Current Ratio, Firm Age, and Market-to-Book.

The Pecking Order Theory describes corporate financing behaviour as following a preferred sequence of funding options: (1) using retained earnings, (2) borrowing, and (3) issuing shares. Therefore, enterprises prefer to use internal funds first due to the lower cost of raising funds and to avoid the risk of asymmetric information. The theory outlines a bidirectional relationship between a firm's financial performance and its tendency to hold cash. Organisations with elevated ROA are inclined to build up cash reserves as a means of capitalising on investment prospects and navigating financial challenges (Ali et al., 2016). Nevertheless, specific research indicates that elevated ROA can lead to a reduction in CCH as the firm allocates gains towards investments or debt repayment (Aftab et al., 2018). In an emerging market characterised by appealing and accessible investment opportunities, we propose a positive association between ROA and CCH behaviour. Our hypothesis suggests that:

H3: The return on total assets positively affects CCH behaviour.

Managers may be inclined to accumulate cash in order to strengthen their control over firm assets and obtain discretionary authority over investment decisions. With cash on hand, the executive is not required to find external funding or submit extensive details about the company's investment initiatives to the financial markets. Organisations with greater investment opportunities are expected to maintain larger cash balances to ensure the availability of resources needed to pursue growth projects. According to Chen et al. (2015), Tayem (2017) and Aftab et al. (2018), the use of the market-to-book ratio (MTBR) as a proxy would lead to a positive association between investment opportunities and CCH. As a result, our next hypothesis is:

H4: MTBR is significantly and positively associated with CCH behaviour.

The maturity of debt (DEBM) influences CCH. While Jung and Choi (2024) identify a positive relationship between DEBM and CCH, Batuman et al. (2022) provide evidence of the opposite association, where a decrease (or increase) in debt maturity leads to higher (or lower) CCH. From these empirical findings, it can be hypothesised that:

H5: DEBM and CCH behaviour are negatively related to each other.

Capital structure is a characteristic often considered in models of factors influencing CCH behaviour. Firms with stronger short-term solvency tend to keep more cash on hand as a safeguard against financial risk, indicating a prudent and flexible financial policy (Farida & Nuryadin, 2023). So, our next hypothesis is:

H6: Current Ratio (CURR) and CCH behaviour are positively related to each other.

CCH behaviour differs according to the age and maturity of firms, as well as their operating and investment opportunities. Ki and Adhikari (2023) discovered that newer firms generally hold higher cash reserves compared to older, more established firms, with the marginal utility of these CCH being greater for newer firms. On the other hand, mature and senior firms typically maintain lower cash holdings, likely due to stronger financial stability, improved creditworthiness, and a reduced need to manage financial risks. Considering the points discussed, it may be proposed that:

H7: Firm age (FAGE) has a substantial negative effect on CCH behaviour.

Security analysts and investors regard the market-to-book ratio (MTB) as an indicator of value. Elyasiani & Movaghari (2024) identify a hump-shaped relationship between MTB and CCH in US firms, in which CCH increases as MTB rises from low to moderate levels, but begins to decline once MTB exceeds a certain threshold. However, we believe it is possible to propose the following hypothesis in the context of an emerging economy like Vietnam:

H8: Market-to-book (MTB) has a negative correlation to CCH behaviour.

Macroeconomic conditions and CCH behaviour

The literature shows that firms alter their CCH behaviour as a reaction to changes in macroeconomic factors. Extensive evidence suggests that persistent inflation hurts long-term economic growth. The opportunity cost of holding currency, distortions in relative pricing, and the tax system significantly influence incentives for investment and saving, which have been issues of theoretical discourse concerning the adverse impacts of inflation (Das et al., 2024). According to Anand et al. (2018), when interest rates rise and currencies appreciate, firms hold less cash than normal. Das et al. (2024) find a positive association between GDP growth and cash holdings. The positive impact of GDP growth aligns with the income effect related to the money demand theory. Firms seek to retain greater cash reserves during economic expansion to ensure sufficient internal capital for financing forthcoming lucrative investment possibilities.

In this paper, we examine the impact of three macroeconomic conditions on CCH behaviour, namely Real Interest Rate, Inflation, and GDP growth, with the following hypotheses:

H9: Real Interest Rate is associated negatively with CCH behaviour.

H10: Inflation is associated negatively with CCH behaviour.

H11: GDP growth has a positive association with CCH behaviour.

Methods

Based on the data analysis method used, we propose two research models as follows:

$$\text{CASHCL} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{SIZAS} + \alpha_2 \text{LEVE} + \alpha_3 \text{ROA} + \alpha_4 \text{MTBR} + \alpha_5 \text{DEBM} + \alpha_6 \text{CURR} + \alpha_7 \text{FAGE} + \alpha_8 \text{MTB} + \alpha_9 \text{RIR} + \alpha_{10} \text{INF} + \alpha_{11} \text{GDP} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CASHD} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{SIZAS} + \alpha_2 \text{LEVE} + \alpha_3 \text{ROA} + \alpha_4 \text{MTBR} + \alpha_5 \text{DEBM} + \alpha_6 \text{CURR} + \alpha_7 \text{FAGE} + \alpha_8 \text{MTB} + \alpha_9 \text{RIR} + \alpha_{10} \text{INF} + \alpha_{11} \text{GDP} + \epsilon_t \quad (2)$$

As of December 31, 2023, there are 61 transport firms listed on the two stock exchanges in Vietnam: HNX and HOSE. After excluding one company due to insufficient data for the period 2016–2023, a total of 60 companies were included in the research sample (HNX: 26, HOSE: 34). The primary data source is collected from annual reports and company websites. From the literature review described above, it can be seen that the relevant variables in this study can be formulated through the mental framework, as shown in Figure 1 below. The sampling technique employed is a purposive sampling method, which involves a time series sampling approach spanning 8 years from 2016 to 2023.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 below presents the characteristics of the dataset used in this study, including the mean, standard deviations, and minimum and maximum values of both independent and dependent variables for the entire sample.

Table 1. Vietnam's transport firms descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
CASHD	480	0,1175662	0,0993901	0,000359	0,7282303
CASHCL	480	0,8492645	1.282.016	0,0012247	11,5907
SIZAS	480	11,85983	0,6509394	10,63687	13,98444
LEVE	480	1,310078	6,12718	-6,484646	119,2909
ROA	480	0,0837433	0,1064991	-0,3438826	0,552339
MTBR	453	0,7453856	1,343617	-0,936966	10,65828
DEBM	480	0,2504376	0,2407187	0	0,8589491
CURR	480	3,923817	5,0520970	0,2380294	35,87174
FAGE	480	1,336098	0,2324558	0,30103	1,838849
MTB	453	1,891078	4,8283880	-2,78411	97,7913
RIR	480	0,0479778	0,0138281	0,0259151	0,0727803
INF	480	0,0299863	0,0052599	0,0183472	0,0353963
GDP	480	0,0588044	0,0201334	0,0255373	0,0812351

The descriptive statistics, reported in Table 1, show that during the period from 2016 to 2023, listed transport firms in Vietnam had an average cash holding ratio (CASHD) of 11.7%, with a high of 72.8%. The cash ratio (CASHCL) averages around 8,5%, and the highest reaches 11,6%. Compared to the cash holding ratios in previous studies, this level is relatively high. The difference may be due to the varying sample sizes and different study periods. The cash

holding ratio found in Le et al. (2018) For a sample of UK firms over the period 2011-2016, around 7.8%. Aftab et al. (2018) examined 5,957 firms across 47 countries between 2007 and 2016, categorised into six regions (including Europe, Asia Pacific, North America, Africa, South America, and the Middle East), and found that the average cash holding was 14.8%.

Correlation explains the interaction between two variables, specifically how a change in one variable influences the other. The result in Table 2 below shows that: CASHD and CASHCL are both negatively correlated with firm size (SIZAS: -0.1240*** and -0.2008***), financial leverage (LEVE: -0.1126** and -0.1029**), debt maturity (DEBM: -0.1395***), and firm age (FAGE: -0.1572*** and -0.0845*), suggesting that larger, more indebted, and older firms tend to hold less cash, possibly because they have easier access to finance or more stable cash flows. In contrast, CASHD is positively correlated with profitability (ROA: 0.1046**), suggesting that highly profitable firms tend to hold more cash to finance investment opportunities or reduce financial risk. In particular, CASHCL has a strong positive correlation with the liquidity ratio (CURR: 0.4281***), indicating that highly liquid firms tend to hold more cash on hand.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix

Variable	CASHD	CASHCL	SIZAS	LEVE	ROA	MTBR	DEBM	CURR	FAGE	MTB	RIR	INF	GDP
CASHD	1.0000												
CASHCL	0.6324***	1.0000											
SIZAS	-0.1240***	-0.2008***	1.0000										
LEVE	-0.1126**	-0.1029**	0.2301***	1.0000									
ROA	0.1046**	0.0367	0.0022	-0.1849***	1.0000								
MTBR	0.0541	0.2217***	-0.1133**	-0.1388***	0.5361***	1.0000							
DEBM	-0.1395***	-0.1416***	0.3928***	0.0025	-0.1784***	-0.2832***	1.0000						
CURR	-0.0257	0.4281***	-0.1938***	-0.1137**	0.1142**	0.2621***	-0.2914***	1.0000					
FAGE	-0.1572***	-0.0845*	0.0969**	0.1279***	-0.1659***	-0.1741***	0.0683	-0.0829*	1.0000				
MTB	-0.0358	-0.0234	0.1605***	0.8315***	0.0156	0.2485***	-0.0501	-0.0347	0.0582	1.0000			
RIR	-0.0412	-0.0669	0.0304	-0.0019	-0.0859*	-0.0280	-0.0317	0.0154	0.1130**	-0.0100	1.0000		
INF	-0.0077	-0.0197	0.0041	-0.0803*	0.0667	-0.0264	0.0318	-0.0214	-0.0286	-0.1105**	-0.2031***	1.0000	
GDP	0.0119	0.0114	-0.0178	-0.0703	0.1383***	-0.0293	0.0542	-0.0078	-0.0789*	-0.0930**	-0.5239***	0.4952***	1.0000

Table 3. Regression results

	CASHD				CASHCL			
	(1) OLS	(2) FEM	(3) REM	(4) FGLS	(1) OLS	(2) FEM	(3) REM	(4) SGLS
SIZAS	-0.0103 (0.0081)	-0.0543 (0.0417)	-0.0184 (0.0129)	-0.0084 (0.0058)	-0.2367** (0.0966)	0.1427 (0.5114)	-0.2551* (0.1502)	-0.0779** (0.0397)
LEVE	-0.0055*** (0.0018)	-0.0010 (0.0039)	-0.0042* (0.0024)	-0.0045*** (0.0010)	0.0040 (0.0211)	-0.0181 (0.0477)	0.0008 (0.0290)	-0.0051 (0.0130)
ROA	0.0705 (0.0527)	0.1213* (0.0617)	0.0899 (0.0550)	0.0613* (0.0341)	-1.3071** (0.6314)	-0.8514 (0.7580)	-0.9163 (0.6683)	-0.2217 (0.2616)
MTBR	-0.0113** (0.0055)	0.0110 (0.0085)	-0.0021 (0.0065)	-0.0013 (0.0046)	0.1839*** (0.0653)	0.2455** (0.1047)	0.2023*** (0.0783)	0.0939** (0.0457)
DEBM	-0.0571** (0.0227)	0.0112 (0.0374)	-0.0129 (0.0287)	-0.0387** (0.0158)	0.2475 (0.2724)	0.4039 (0.4591)	0.5184 (0.3436)	0.1273 (0.0930)
CURR	-0.0017* (0.0010)	0.0019 (0.0014)	0.0003 (0.0011)	-0.0012 (0.0009)	0.0959*** (0.0115)	0.1554*** (0.0167)	0.1233*** (0.0136)	0.1206*** (0.0142)
FAGE	-0.0545** (0.0220)	-0.1141 (0.0915)	-0.0597* (0.0355)	-0.0471** (0.0207)	-0.1562 (0.2635)	-3.0056*** -11238	-0.3431 (0.4134)	-0.1227 (0.1231)
MTB	0.0060** (0.0023)	0.0010 (0.0049)	0.0049 (0.0031)	0.0054*** (0.0012)	-0.0142 (0.0279)	0.0166 (0.0596)	-0.0059 (0.0369)	0.0055 (0.0161)
RIR	-0.1903 (0.3933)	0.0453 (0.3506)	-0.1248 (0.3315)	0.0120 (0.1779)	-69397 - 47130	-24452 - 43044	-65147 - 40718	0.5008 (0.9957)
INF	-0.5438 - 10118	-0.2958 (0.8368)	-0.3758 (0.8436)	-0.3007 (0.3847)	-57311 - 121255	-31558 - 102720	-38810 - 103769	-0.6449 - 21088
GDP	-0.0412 (0.3066)	-0.1232 (0.2552)	-0.0834 (0.2566)	-0.0390 (0.1267)	-0.2029 - 36746	-13427 - 31330	-0.8795 - 31560	0.8119 (0.6950)
_cons	0.3600*** (0.1026)	0.8987* (0.4574)	0.4294*** (0.1569)	0.2848*** (0.0698)	3.9380*** - 12292	26483 - 56150	4.1300** - 18287	1.2626*** (0.4755)
N	453	453	453	453	453	453	453	453
R-sq	0.075	0.064	0	0	0.223	0.239	0	0

Standard errors in parentheses

* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Figure 1. *The relationship between the factors and CASHD and CASHCL*

Due to the different methods used to measure cash holdings, the results can vary. CASHD reflects the cash management strategy within total assets, while CASHCL reflects the financial structure, indicating the firm's ability to pay short-term debts. Specifically:

The negative coefficient in all 4 models of CASHD is not statistically significant. This suggests that firm size does not significantly impact the CCH ratio of transport companies. For CASHCL, SIZAS is negative and significant in OLS ($p < 0.05$), REM ($p < 0.1$), and GLS ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that larger firms generally maintain lower cash holdings compared to their short-term debt. This could be due to larger firms having easier access to financing, which reduces the necessity to hold cash. The results are in accordance with Chen et al. (2015), Tayem (2017), and Das et al. (2024) but in contradiction with Ali et al. (2016), Aftab et al. (2018), Diaw (2021), and Batuman et al. (2022). This evidence supports hypothesis H1. Due to scale advantages and informational imbalances, smaller firms in emerging markets like Vietnam tend to maintain higher cash holdings, whereas larger firms maintain lower cash holdings to manage their daily transactions and operational activities. Larger firms are able to secure external financing more easily, decreasing their need to hold cash. On the other hand, this effect is more pronounced when looking at total short-term debt (CASHCL), as larger firms can rely on trade credit rather than cash reserves.

Financial leverage (LEVE) has a negative and highly statistically significant impact on CASHD in OLS and GLS. But the recorded results for the CASHCL model are not statistically significant. This indicates that firms with high leverage often incur significant financial costs, prompting them to reduce their cash reserves. The negative impact of LEVE on CASHD supports hypothesis H2, aligning with the results from earlier research by Ali et al. (2016), Tayem (2017), and Diaw (2021), Batuman et al. (2022) and Das et al. (2024). However, when compared to short-term debt (CASHCL), the impact is unclear because the firms can use borrowed money to maintain liquidity. The impact of financial performance (ROA) on CASHD is positive and statistically significant in FEM and GLS, whereas for CASHCL, the coefficient is negative and statistically significant in OLS. It shows that firms with high profitability (high ROA) tend to accumulate more cash (positive impact on CASHD), similar to the results in Ali et al. (2016), supporting hypothesis H3. However, high profits can also lead companies to invest more in other assets, reducing cash compared to short-term debt (negative impact on CASHCL), which is also explained by Aftab et al. (2018).

The effect of MTBR on CASHD is unstable and negative in OLS, contrasting with the result proven by Tayem (2017). This evidence does not support the predictions of the trade-off and pecking order theories. However, for the CASHCL model, the coefficient is positive and significant in all models, supporting hypothesis H4. This suggests that firms with a high MTBR may hold cash on hand to capitalise on potential investment opportunities, thereby increasing the CASHCL ratio. However, when considering total assets (CASHD), firms can use cash to purchase other earning assets, resulting in a negative effect.

Effect of DEBM on CASHD: For the CASHD model, the effect is negative in OLS and GLS. For the CASHCL model, it is not statistically significant. Hypothesis H5 is supported, consistent with the research results of Batuman et al. (2022). The maturity of a firm's debt decreases (or increases), resulting in the firm having more (or less) cash.

There is no significance in most of the models analysing the impact of CURR on CASHD. Hypothesis H6 is rejected, contrary to the results of Farida and Nuryadin (2023). In the CASHCL model, the impact is positive and highly significant. It indicates that a high liquidity index suggests the firm has increased its short-term assets, resulting in a higher cash balance compared to short-term debt (CASHCL). However, when considering total assets (CASHD), this impact is not clear because the firm can allocate cash to other assets.

FAGE has a negative and significant effect on CASHD but is insignificant in most of the CASHCL models, except for FEM. Hypothesis H7 is confirmed, similar to the conclusion of Ki & Adhikari (2023). Thus, older firms tend to have more stable financial systems, reducing the need to hold cash. However, when considering short-term debt (CASHCL), this effect is not apparent because firms can adjust cash flows more flexibly.

MTB has a positive and significant effect on CASHD in OLS and GLS. Hypothesis H8 is rejected; this result is contrary to the result of Elyasiani and Movaghari (2024). Thus, the higher the company's value, the more cash it holds, thereby reducing the need to hold cash. For the CASHCL model, it is not statistically significant.

The impact of macroeconomic conditions (RIR, INF, GDP): No variable has strong statistical significance in both models. This indicates that real interest rates (RIR) and inflation (INF) may influence cash holding decisions, but are unstable in the transport sector due to the nature of long capital cycles. GDP can indirectly influence business efficiency, but it does not have a direct and significant impact on cash holdings. Therefore, hypotheses H9, H10, and H11 are rejected. This result contradicts the studies Anand et al. (2018) and Das et al. (2024).

Conclusion And Recommendations

This study examines the impact of firm size and financial leverage on the cash holding behaviour of listed transport firms in Vietnam. The results suggest that larger firms typically retain less cash than smaller ones, likely due to their superior access to financing. Financial leverage adversely affects cash holdings, as it incurs high financial costs that erode cash reserves. Financial performance has a positive influence on cash holdings, but it exhibits a contrasting effect when considering current liabilities. Firms with high market value typically increase their cash ratio to capitalise on investment opportunities. Furthermore, older firms with stable financial systems maintain lower cash levels. Macroeconomic factors do not significantly influence cash-holding behaviour, emphasising the long capital cycle characteristic of the transport sector. It is essential to support small-scale transport firms in enhancing cash flow management and diversifying funding sources. Such measures can reduce dependence on debt financing, mitigate liquidity risks, and promote more efficient cash utilisation, allowing transport firms to better capitalise on investment opportunities. The study's data coverage is limited to the transport industry, which may

limit its generalizability. Future research could expand its scope to encompass other sectors and include additional macroeconomic factors, providing a more comprehensive perspective.

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